

INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION AS THE BASIS OF THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

In the conditions of modern competition in the market of educational services, the main emphasis is on the viability of a higher educational institution to ensure the production of innovatively active specialists. Specific innovative training within the framework of leading scientific and pedagogical schools brings undoubted benefits to both the scientific community and individual researchers, and especially to production, society, and the economy. Therefore, the integration of science and education in modern higher educational institutions allows us to provide new opportunities for the development of the higher education system. The article talks about the close integration of science and education in higher educational institutions, including pedagogical universities.

Keywords: pedagogical educational institutions, science and education, paradigm, integration, methodology.

In the modern world, the integration of science and education is one of the important trends [2]. The basis of the modern educational process is the field of education, based on scientifically proven and recommended methods. Science purposefully influences the educational process and is capable of changing the structure of education [3]. Features of the modern development of science in higher educational institutions are an important and pressing problem that requires a comprehensive analysis and generalization of a number of areas of research.

The exceptional role of education and intellectual resources in the country's life, the formation of human potential, and its future are among the main conditions of the state's competitiveness. Thus, countries compete not only with services and products, but also with social values and education systems (especially higher education systems). In order to continue competition in the modern world, states rely not on their territory and natural resources, but on their intellectual potential. In the present era, when global changes are proceeding rapidly, every country and society has a great need for highly educated, innovative-minded specialists. The modern world is characterized by the rapid increase of information resources, the rise of the knowledge system, and the frequent replacement of events [A new stage].

Our future is related to the development of science and education, this is the issue of the future of every country and nation. Science and education are the main areas that determine our development prospects. The success of the country is determined by knowledge, science, technology and education. In the modern era, there are several indicators of the success of the development of the countries of the world. Among them, the current stage of development of science and education plays a very important role. Science and education are one of the main factors that enable every person to shape their sustainable future, to acquire the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes and values.

One of the most urgent problems facing science and education in the complex age we live in is the issue of formation of world-viewing, scientific, professional staff potential. In the course of development of the modern world, the greatest factor that can change not

only people, but perhaps an entire nation, is the phenomenon of science and education. For this reason, the countries of the world pay special attention to the development of science, apply new methods to increase the level of education, and allocate a large part of their budgets to the development of science and education. If we look at the dynamics of the development of the countries of the world, we will see that they have reached their position in the world arena thanks to their success in science and education.

Features of the modern development of science in higher educational institutions are a significant and pressing problem that requires a comprehensive analysis and generalization of many research areas. The question is asked: what is the current ratio of educational and scientific knowledge implemented in the conditions of a higher educational institution, including a higher pedagogical educational institution.

Unfortunately, there are several acute problems. First of all, there is the obvious resource unpreparedness of the entire current system of teacher training for the implementation of those large-scale innovative goals that are set today for modern teachers and higher educational institutions. To integrate science into the educational process, a teacher must change the traditional approach to his professional activities. To introduce science into the innovative process of education, students must also change, including future teachers who study at pedagogical universities. The list of personal and professional qualities that even beginning teachers must demonstrate as a result of the implementation of current standards cannot be formed in young people during their studies in four-year bachelor's programs. The current situation is one of the reasons for the emergence of a draft new teacher standard, which entails the need to update the standards of teacher education in general, since the existing ones have great difficulty "catching up" with the new realities.

Education and science in modern conditions, developing independently and independently of each other, are becoming less and less self-sufficient and capable. These social systems in the new conditions need to draw up a synthesis, which involves the consistent implementation of a set of integration projects and programs. The best specialists are trained where there is a

close relationship between the educational process and research and development work, where there is an opportunity to become involved in the activities of leading scientific teams, feel the atmosphere of scientific research, and take part in the development of major projects. Fundamental scientific achievements, major technical solutions, the latest technologies and developments, original innovative projects appear, as a rule, in those research organizations where there is harmony. More and more research emphasizes that the development of society based on the integration of modern social systems of education and science in general is a national strategic task.

In modern conditions, there are serious problems in the systems of science and education, which are based on the following main contradictions [4, 5]:

- discrepancy between the theoretical and methodological content of education and the level of development of modern scientific knowledge;
- in the absence of a theoretical fundamental concept for the development of modern domestic education;
- in the absence of scientific theoretical and methodological validity of innovative educational technologies.

Science is woven into all spheres of human activity; it is also introduced into the basic foundations of relationships among people themselves. Its role in education is especially significant. The modern educational process is based on a scientific picture of the world. And the sphere of education itself is based on scientifically proven and recommended methods. The modern educational system opposes the routine principle of education, which implements the principle "Do as I do!", with scientifically based approaches that take into account the peculiarities of the neurophysiological, mental and emotional-volitional sphere of activity of the subjects of the educational process. The role of science in education extends to all components of the educational process: goals, means, results, principles, forms and methods. Scientific meanings act as the main units of the educational matrix; they include the personality of the student in the real process of life.

Higher education plays an important role in the development of science. It is appropriate to recall that in all advanced countries science develops, first of all, in universities and brings in huge income. Higher education science is seen as a powerful innovative resource for the development of the entire education system.

The traditional role of higher education institutions - the transfer of knowledge to society in the form of education and training of specialists to meet the needs of the economy - is increasingly becoming clearly insufficient. A modern university can and should have a direct impact on the development of fundamental knowledge and practically targeted innovation. Therefore, today the priority tasks are the development and support of fundamental science and university education.

The development of research activities and scientific and technical creativity of students is an integral part of the modernization of education. The integration

of science and education in the living educational process helps to improve the quality of personnel training, the development of the creative initiative of young people, their active participation in solving issues related to inventive and rationalization activities, and the search for effective, advanced, non-standard solutions to scientific and technical problems. In the era of innovative development of society, specialists who have not only high professional knowledge, but also skills in organizational, educational, and management work and who have their own scientific worldview are becoming necessary and in demand in the intellectual labor market. Scientific research in universities determines the guarantees and conditions for training highly qualified specialists.

In the search for a new paradigm of education, innovative processes are the only sources of development of the education system. New types of educational organizations, management systems, new technologies and methods are manifestations of the enormous potential of innovative processes. Competent and thoughtful implementation of them helps to deepen positive changes in it.

In this regard, the problem of ensuring the quality of training of specialists with higher education is relevant in the context of implementing an innovative approach, solving complex problems associated with improving the quality of training of specialists and the inclusion of the educational system in the innovation processes of other countries. I would especially like to note the definition of the main forms of participation of higher educational institutions in various international events, the identification of the scope of activity and the designation of a range of problems around the solution of which international activity in the future can be concentrated.

Today, science and education serve not only the cultural development of society, improving people's living conditions, material well-being, but also the conditions for preventing negative trends and primitive acts of thinking that social institutions have tried to eliminate since ancient times. times, with virtually no administrative intervention. Leaving aside the well-known achievements of science and education, facts prove that in countries with a high level of science and education, even criminal cases rarely arise, and the fight against these unpleasant cases is carried out according to civilized rules.

World experience shows that to build an economy in these areas and ensure its sustainability, first of all, high technologies, efficient production, innovative entrepreneurship and advanced management systems and technologies are needed. In this process, which involves the formation of a knowledge economy based on innovation in the country, the unity of science and education, their integration into world science and education, is undoubtedly one of the main upcoming tasks.

Today, creating a strong scientific environment in higher education institutions and caring for research institutes have become important issues. The United States and Western countries have long recognized the unity of science and education and have been able to

create strong think tanks and intellectual environments in higher education institutions. Thus, higher education specialists grow up as personnel with strong scientific potential, meeting international standards and distinguished by intellectual abilities.

The specifics and conditions for the development of scientific knowledge at the present stage also determine the specifics of the functioning of knowledge in education: the deepening disciplinary complexity of scientific knowledge entails a change in the structural system of educational knowledge, forming its fragmentation and episodic nature. Of significant importance in the functioning of scientific and educational knowledge in the modern information society is the fundamental coincidence of the processes of scientific knowledge and educational knowledge, when the processes of training and education occur on the basis of active scientific research.

Integration processes continue to be the leading trend in the development of modern science, one of the most important factors ensuring scientific and technological progress. In such a situation, the functioning of education outside the context of science is impossible "The effectiveness and efficiency of solving scientific, technical and social pressing problems of our time depends on how deeply the theoretical foundations of integration processes are revealed." That is why a philosophical analysis of the modern specifics of the processes of integration of education and science is required to the same extent as the practical implementation of a complex of integration projects.

The formation of skills in conducting scientific activities among students is carried out already in the process of preparing final qualifying works, which require the mandatory implementation of the scientific principle. Consequently, student scientific work is a continuation and deepening of the educational process and is usually organized directly at the departments. However, students' research work must also be organized during extracurricular time, and it is carried out in the form of work in scientific circles, participation in conferences organized by higher educational institutions, as well as participation in international scientific conferences online through the global network.

The main areas of scientific research in higher pedagogical educational institutions include the following:

- development of methodology and methods for studying innovative processes and innovative activities in education,
- methodology and methods for their improvement,
- development of models of innovation activity systems in educational organizations of various types,
- development of models for supporting innovative activities in education at the regional level,
- development of educational programs and didactic tools for training and advanced training of education workers in the field of innovation.

In our opinion, the main priority issue in pedagogically oriented universities at present is the existence of science and education in the form of unity. It is impossible to separate scientific research and educational programs implemented in higher education institutions. Because specialists must be trained to conduct any scientific research. There must be appropriate programs for their development. We have to approach the preparation of a scientific researcher in stages. To improve the quality of training in higher education institutions, it is important to have the conditions and environment for conducting the most advanced scientific research. From this point of view, the development of science is a relevant topic along with education in pedagogical universities. Today, teachers cannot be trained within the traditional paradigm. More active development of teacher education is possible only in conditions of integration with scientific knowledge. Pedagogical universities today must change in order to maintain their status as an independent element of the general higher education system. To achieve this, we see only one way: to become a higher educational institution of a new type, training teachers based on a combination of innovative educational technologies and pedagogical scientific achievements.

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